

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

ANALYSIS OF FINANCIAL SUPPORT FOR BUSINESS ENTITIES IN UZBEKISTAN

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes theoretical bases and approaches financial support for business entities by government. It also analyzes the current state of state support for business entities in Uzbekistan and develops proposals and recommendations for its further improvement.

Keywords. advanced economy, emerging economy, entrepreneurship, financial support, tax policy.

Introduction.

The widespread use of economic factors, in particular the tax system, as an incentive factor in the development of the activities of business entities in Uzbekistan is also recognized as an important factor. Thus, the development of the activities of small businesses and private entrepreneurs requires a systematic assessment of the impact of the tax policy applied to them, first of all. Achieving sustainable economic growth is a priority goal of governments around the world, and encouraging entrepreneurship and providing financial support from the state are important components of achieving this goal. One of the most appropriate ways to stimulate economic growth, innovation, and create new jobs is entrepreneurial activity. Increasing the share of small and medium-sized businesses in GDP through financial support from the state, including increasing the GDP per capita, and improving the well-being of the population by ensuring employment, is an objective necessity.

The determination of specific areas of state financial support for business entities in order to achieve the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) announced by the United Nations (UN), and the unwavering pursuit of these priorities, is a factor in the sustainable development of the country's economy.

Literature review.

The positive aspects of state financial support for business entities have been widely covered in scientific research. In particular, as economists R. Ismail and N. Usman (2014) state in their research, "State financial support for small business entities serves as a factor in the development of healthy competition between small and medium-sized business entities. Also, the provision of marketing services by the state has a positive effect on business growth. State support for conducting marketing research is important in order to use the potential of small and medium-sized business support agencies and thus increase the effectiveness of relevant government support programs. If the developers of state economic policy use the results of marketing research as a reference in the formation of future financial support programs, then the executive bodies implementing this policy, i.e. ministries and departments, will facilitate the integration of business entities into global markets, technology and financial markets".

According to economist F. Peter et al (2018), "The government should eliminate all unnecessary bureaucratic barriers and favoritism, and establish a strategic

and robust venture capital sector to provide crowdfunding and other sources of financing at affordable prices to important sectors such as agriculture and industrial production. This measure should help form new business entities and expand existing small businesses and private entrepreneurs, create new jobs while establishing local production for the comprehensive socio-economic development of regions, and central and local government authorities and management bodies should make more extensive use of opportunities to effectively stimulate business entities through taxes within their powers".

According to the author, the wide introduction of a package of financial assistance such as tax breaks and preferences, favorable bank loans and investments is an important key to business success. Therefore, financial assistance provided by the state to business entities requires regular monitoring.

Economists D. Xiang and A. Worthington (2017) found that "state financial support helps small and medium-sized businesses to increase their efficiency compared to the influence of traditional financing sources. Also, business entities using the financial support package provided by the state should refrain from becoming participants in the "hidden economy", otherwise the advantages of financial support provided by the state compared to traditional financing to causes the "shadow" to fall. Controlling factors of the activity of business entities include the size of the business, the degree of introduction of innovations, the achievement of business goals and the degree of localization of industrial production".

We believe that the correct and targeted use of financial assistance provided by the state by business entities will serve the development of their activities. The development of business activities serves to solve such issues at the central and local levels as social: employment; growth of the population's well-being; economic: the establishment of the production of semi-finished and finished products from local raw materials, the emergence of new types of services, and ultimately the creation of an added value chain.

Another group of scholars, M. Anwar and Q. Li (2021), while comparing the positive and negative aspects of state financial support, noted the following: "Firstly, small and medium-sized businesses fail due to limited resources and unsatisfactory support, therefore, the Government should not stop providing financial

and non-financial assistance to small and medium-sized businesses. Financial support from the state significantly increases the financial indicators of small and medium-sized businesses; secondly, their impact on the environment is unsatisfactory in relation to the number of small and medium-sized businesses. The reason for this problem is that small and medium-sized businesses do not have sufficient resources to implement successful environmental practices. When responsible agencies increase financial and non-financial support for small and medium-sized businesses and provide additional incentives, they should pay attention to environmental problems and determine the directions of development of activities, taking this program into account in their policies; Thirdly, at the initial stage, small businesses and entrepreneurship may not have sufficient financial resources to launch their operations. Therefore, providing access to state financial resources on preferential terms compared to high-interest bank loans from commercial banks will lead to a new stage in the development of small businesses and entrepreneurship; Fourthly, small businesses and entrepreneurship can constantly revise their costs, improve their financial indicators by differentiating products and services (for example, sustainable competitive advantage). However, sustainable competitive advantage requires the attention of the Government from the point of view of the need to create a healthy competitive environment by the State. Therefore, the Government should constantly focus on financial and non-financial incentives for small and medium-sized businesses, which will ensure high economic growth and sustainable socio-economic development”.

Pergelova and Angulo-Ruiz (2014), who conducted research on the evaluation of the policy of financial support for business entities in the United States, “Using new US firms, the impact of government financial support measures - government loans, guarantees and public capital - on the general competitive advantage of firms and on more specific types of competitive advantage based on innovation, licensing, marketing and human capital was studied. The results, controlling for family financing, bank financing, business angel and venture capitalist capital, industry, size, as well as entrepreneur characteristics, show that government guarantees and public capital have a direct and indirect impact on the competitive advantage of new

firms. Policymakers, federal, state and municipal leaders should pay attention to helping newly established small businesses and entrepreneurs adapt to the market and create the necessary opportunities for successful competition”.

Economists Songling et al. (2018) "assessing the impact of competition on the development of small business and entrepreneurial activity, he emphasized that financial support from the state has priority over competition in the development of small business and entrepreneurial activity".

Our research shows that when it comes to the development of entrepreneurial entities and their financial support in the world, special attention is paid to the Barney theory. This theory is “important for entrepreneurship research. Entrepreneurial opportunities can be expressed as an entrepreneur’s unique understanding of the value of certain resources that established firms do not have. This theory also emphasizes the pursuit of uniqueness rather than the pursuit of becoming the best company in all indicators in the future.

Barney et al. (2007) argue that “if an entrepreneur has all the resources needed to carry out his entrepreneurial activity, coordination and control of activities are important. Conversely, when an entrepreneur lacks one or more key resources, he will need internal and external sources of financial support”.

According to Barney’s theory, "the resources that are important for entrepreneurs include: specialized information available to entrepreneurs or their social networks, leadership skills, education and experience (explicit and tacit knowledge), and initiative".

Methodology.

When preparing a scientific article for publication, research methods such as grouping, monographic observation, and comparison were used.

Analysis and results.

As a result of the reforms implemented in Uzbekistan, the share of small businesses in the gross domestic product is increasing year by year. Among several factors, the most important is the reduction in the single tax rate paid by small businesses, which has a positive effect. We assess this situation by analyzing the dynamics of changes in the participation of entrepreneurship and small businesses in the sectors of the economy presented in Table 1.

Table #1.

Dynamics of entrepreneurship and small business participation in economic sectors ¹

Indicators	2019 FY	2020 FY	2021 FY	2022 FY	2023 FY
The share of business entities in the produced GDP, in percent	56	54,8	54,1	51,8	51,2
Volume of industrial products, billion soums	83344,2	103020,8	124907,9	143892,7	176523,9
Production volume of agricultural, forestry and fishery products (services), billion soums	219466,9	253238,2	304452,1	344134,5	403974,4
Construction, billion soums	53960,9	63866,6	77907,1	93554,5	111914
Retail turnover, billion soums	138920,7	164106,1	186759,3	229166,7	273439,8
Volume of services, billion soums	103106,6	114052,7	147061,6	181245	224443,7
Shipping, million tons	641	638,9	550,1	608,2	664,7
Volume of freight turnover, million tons	12152,3	12304,6	13803,2	14843,8	15823,7
Passenger transportation, million people	5345	4904,8	5485,2	5628,4	5743
Passenger traffic, million passengers/km	117412,7	107766,7	120964,7	124433,9	127247,8
Share of products (works, services) in export, in percent	27	20,5	20	29,6	29
Product (works, services) share in imports, in percent	61,6	51,7	45,3	49,4	45,7
Employment, in percent	76,2	74,5	74,5	73,9	74,1

Calculated by the author.

According to Table 1, the share of small business and entrepreneurship in the country's GDP was 56 percent in fiscal year 2019, but decreased by 1.2 percentage points in 2020, by 0.7 percentage points in 2021 compared to 2020, by 2.3 percentage points in 2022 compared to 2021, and by 0.6 percentage points in 2023 compared to 2022. If we list the main reasons for this decrease, small business entities are classified according to various criteria. In the early years of independence, the number of employees was taken as a criterion, and the criteria for obtaining small business status were established based on it.

In order to further stimulate the rapid development of small businesses in Uzbekistan and radically increase their importance and share in the country's economy, this practice was adopted, in which the small business entity standard was based only on the number of employees, without taking into account factors and criteria such as the volume of products produced, the turnover of the small business entity, and the amount of income.

As a result of the above measures, it is appropriate to admit that the share of small business in GDP has decreased. Continuing this analysis, we consider the dynamics of population employment in business entities in Table 2.

Table #2.

Dynamics of changes in total employment of small business entities in the Republic of Uzbekistan and its regions, in percent

Regions	2019 FY	2020 FY	2021 FY	2022 FY	2023 FY
Republic of Karakalpakstan	74,9	74,2	74,2	74,1	74,8
Andijan	82,1	80,8	80,7	80,2	81
Bukhara	76,1	74,9	74,2	74,3	74,3
Jizzakh	79,7	78,4	78,8	77,3	77
Kashkadarya	78,5	78,1	78,5	78,2	77,5
Navoi	55	51,9	52,3	51,1	51,4
Namangan	82,8	81,6	82,2	81	80,6
Samarkand	82,8	81,7	81,5	80,9	81,3
Surkhandarya	79,6	78,2	78,4	76,9	77,2
Syrdarya	76,4	74,5	74,4	72,9	72,4
Tashkent region	72,8	70,8	69,8	70	70,3
Fergana	79,4	78,4	78,5	78,7	79,3
Khorezm	80,4	79,3	79,1	78,1	79,4
Tashkent city	53,7	49,7	50,2	50	49,7
TOTAL	76,2	74,5	74,5	73,9	74,1

Prepared by the author.

¹ Муаллиф ишланмаси (<https://stat.uz/uz/>) - Ўзбекистон Республикаси миллий статистика қўмитаси расмий сайти маълумотлари асосида).

According to Table 2, on average, about 75% of the total working-age population in the republic is employed in entrepreneurial entities. By region, the share of the population employed in small business and entrepreneurial entities above the average in the republic in 2019-2023 was on average 80% in Andijan and Khorezm regions, 81% in Namangan and Samarkand regions, 78% in Jizzakh, Kashkadarya, Surkhandarya and Fergana regions, and 73% in Syrdarya region, 70% in Tashkent region, and 50% in Navoi region and Tashkent city.

In conclusion, the changes introduced in the criteria for determining small business entities can be explained. It can also be assessed as a result of the slow implementation of the task in the republic of "developing regional and sectoral programs to ensure employment of the population based on a thorough analysis of the real situation in the labor market across the regions of our republic and coordinating their implementation, developing state orders for the creation of new jobs, and implementing a comprehensive set of targeted measures to determine the quota of jobs for socially vulnerable segments of the population."

Conclusion

It is known from the laws and principles of economic theory that the state regulates the economy in two ways through fiscal and monetary policy. From this point of view, it is important to correctly apply these two policies in the financial support of small businesses and entrepreneurs. The reason is that the full application of the principles of taxation is one of the important tasks of economic development. Tax-budget policy should be developed taking into account important indicators such as the country's economic situation, the level of socio-economic development of regions, the solvency of economic agents - business entities, and the well-being of the population. As a result, the tax-budget policy has a comprehensive impact on the stabilization of the economy of the republic, the management of the socially protected, free market economy.

It is necessary to introduce the practice of compensating business entities for the costs of railway transportation associated with the delivery of their products to other regions of the republic, and to fully reimburse exporters for transport costs when exporting their products.

In order to improve the investment and business environment of the regions, it is necessary to provide financial support to business entities by reducing tax rates on certain taxes (profit, turnover tax, property and land taxes of legal entities) for business entities located

in all districts of the Republic of Karakalpakstan and operating in this region.

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